

**INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE IN
DENTISTRY 2023 NOVI SAD**

**PROCEEDINGS
OF THE INTERNATIONAL
SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE IN
DENTISTRY 2023 NOVI SAD**

31st of March 2023 :

Diagnostic and therapeutic principles in dental medicine I

1st of April 2023 :

Diagnostic and therapeutic principles in dental medicine II

CIP - Каталогизacija u publikaciji
Biblioteka Matice srpske, Novi Sad

616.31(082)

The INTERNATIONAL Scientific Conference in Dentistry (2023 ; Novi Sad)
Proceedings of The International Scientific Conference in Dentistry 2023, 31st of March-
1st of April 2023, Novi Sad [Elektronski izvor] / editor Milica Jeremić Knežević. - Novi
Sad : Dentistry Clinic of Vojvodina, 2023

Način pristupa (URL): <https://www.simpozijumstomatologa.rs/wp-content/uploads/2023/04/2023-Proceedings.pdf>. - Opis zasnovan na stanju na dan
11.4.2023. - Nasl. sa naslovnog ekrana. - Bibliografija uz svaki rad.

ISBN 978-86-80894-06-5

a) Stomatologija -- Zbornici

COBISS.SR-ID 113768969

**Organization of this Conference was approved by the Scientific
Council of the Dentistry Clinic of Vojvodina**

Editor: Dr Milica Jeremić Knežević, professor

Publisher: Dentistry Clinic of Vojvodina

Organizing committee

Prof. dr Tatjana Puškar- president

Prof. dr Sanja Vujkov

Dr Marko Gojnić

Dr Milojko Jovanović

Stevan Dragosavljević, MCS

Prof. dr Aleksandra Maletin

Prof. dr Duška Blagojević

Prof. dr Ivan Šarčev

Prof. dr Siniša Mirković

Prof. dr Branislav Bajkin

Prof. dr Ivana Gušić

Prof. dr Bojana Milekić

Teach. Asist. dr Jelena Komšić

Teach. Asist. dr Mirjana Stojšić

Scientific committee

Prof. dr Milica Jeremić Knežević- president (RS)

Prof. dr Igor Budak (RS)

Prof. dr Larisa Blažić (RS)

Prof. dr Đorđe Vukelić (RS)

Prof. dr Bojan Petrović (RS)

Prof. dr Mirjana Bošković (RS)

Prof. dr Anca Jivanescu (RO)

Prof. dr Davor Seifert (CRO)

Prof. dr Jozsef Szalma (HU)

Prof. dr Rebeka Rudolf (SLO)

Prof. dr Zamri Radzi (MAL)

Prof. dr Dominic Eggbeer (UK)

Prof. dr Dubravka Marković (RS)

Dr Petar Ninkov (NOR)

Assist. Prof. dr Branka Trifković (RS)

Assist. Prof. dr Daniela Đurović Koprivica (RS)

Assist. Prof. dr Iva Milinković (RS)

Assist. Prof. dr Ana Todorović (RS)

Assist Prof. dr Dušica Simić Panić (RS)

LIP PRINT PATTERN AS AN IDENTIFICATION TOOL

Veljović T.¹, Veselinović I.^{1,2}, Đurić M.^{1,3}, Gušić I.^{1,3}, Mirnić J.¹, Maletin A.¹, Ramić B.¹, Vukoje K.¹

¹University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Medicine, Novi Sad

²Clinical Centre of Vojvodina, Centre for Forensic Medicine, Novi Sad

³Dentistry Clinic of Vojvodina, Novi Sad

Abstract:

Lip prints are considered an important form of evidence transfer, analogous to fingerprints, as the arrangement of lines on the red part of human lips is unique to each individual and can thus be very useful in forensic investigations and personal identification. Not only are lip prints uniform throughout one's life, but the available evidence shows that, after lip trauma, the lip pattern eventually reverts to that prior to the injury. Although lip prints are commonly found on drinking glasses, cutlery, paper napkins, cigarette butts, and tissues, they can be retrieved from the surface of windows, paintings, doors and plastic bags, making them a useful tool for establishing a link between the subject and the crime scene. In some cases, they can appear on food products alongside bite marks. These prints are a result of humidity present in lips through saliva, mixed with the oils secreted by neighboring salivary and sebaceous glands. These substances, particularly the lipids and fatty acids, are transferred to an object through lip contact which can be rendered visible through different forensic techniques.

The most commonly used classification for recording lip patterns was established by Suzuki and Tsuchihashi by studying the natural lip marks or fissures, resulting in the following six types: Type I – Complete vertical; Type I' – Incomplete vertical; Type II – Branched grooves (Y-shaped pattern); Type III – Intersected grooves; Type IV – Reticular pattern; and Type V – Irregular.

Key words: lip prints, forensic anthropology, personal identification